

(BAP), 0.5 mg indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), 0.5 mg naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), 500 mg casein hydrolysate, and 3% sucrose gelled with 0.8% agar. The calli were incubated at 26-27 °C in continuous 3000 lux light intensity.

Active cell division took place in the scutellum, especially on the subepidermal (sep) portion (see figure, 1-2). Calli formed on day 6 of culture. Elongated structures were visible at the periphery of the scutellum on day 10 (3). Cells pushed out the epithelial layer, giving the scutellum a wavy appearance. Active cell division was visible on day 12. Smooth, compact, round and whitish embryoids were obtained after 3 wk in culture (4).

Anatomical observations showed embryogenic calli with densely packed cells, prominent nucleus, and thin cell walls (5). Nonembryogenic calli had loosely packed cells, hardly visible nuclei, and thick cell walls (5).

Rice embryoid development: 1 = longitudinal section of a seed embryo showing the coleorhiza (cr), coleoptile (cl), scutellum (sc), and subepidermal layer (sep); 2 = callus formation at the subepidermal layer of the sc; 3 = thallus structure proliferating from the surface of the sc; 4 = 3-mo-old smooth, compact, round, and whitish embryoids; 5 = an embryogenic callus; 6 = a nonembryogenic callus; 7 = scanning electron micrograph of embryogenic calli (e) proliferating at the surface of nonembryogenic (ne) calli; 8 = scanning electron micrograph of an embryoid with sc, cr, and a developing cl. IRRI, 1987.

A SEM study (7) showed globular and organized structures (e) proliferating at the surface of the nonembryogenic calli (ne). Embryoids containing the scutellar portion, coleorhiza, and a developing coleoptile (8) were exactly

like the zygotic embryo, but sometimes did not have synchronized development.

Embryogenic calli transferred to regeneration medium produced prolific shoots and plantlets from embryoids after 3 wk in culture. □

Yield potential

Models for predicting rice flowering

A. B. Dua and D. P. Garrity, Multiple Cropping Department, IRRI

Models for predicting flowering in cereals are often location specific. We developed simple temperature-dependent regression models that can estimate flowering in lowland irrigated rice. Data from 43 rice experiments conducted at 23 irrigated sites in Asia, Africa, and Latin America that ranged from 0°9'S latitude (Ahero, Kenya) to 37°16'N latitude (Suweon, Korea) were evaluated for relationships between mean temperature, photoperiod, and flowering date.

Three maturity groups, represented by cultivars IR9729-67-3 (very early), IR36

and BG35-2 (early), and Taichung Sen Yu 285 (medium), were tested for best fit to generalized thermal or photoperiod models. Thermal units (T_u) for each 24-h interval had been recorded in agrometeorological stations in the vicinity of the experiments. Daily thermal units were calculated as the mean of the daily maximum (T_{max}) and minimum (T_{min}) temperatures and summed for the period from seeding to flowering (SF).

Accumulated thermal units for the period transplanting to flowering (TF) also were computed. Photoperiod (p) at panicle initiation was estimated, using meteorological algorithms. Reciprocals of the durations of SF and TF were calculated as the average rate of progress toward flowering. Average rate of progress toward flowering showed a curvilinear trend with mean temperature (see figure). This relationship was derived from data across the four

Rate of development from seeding to flowering of IR36 (1/f) vs mean temperature.

Photo-thermal models for predicting flowering in IR36 across locations. Screened data set of 43 trials from a global rice-weather study. 1987.

Model	Regression coefficients ^a				R ²	CV
	a	b	c	d		
<i>Seeding to flowering</i>						
1. 1/f = a + b*Tmean	-0.00165ns (0.00233)	0.00471** (0.00009)	-	-	0.39	13.0
2. 1/f = a + b* <i>TU</i>	0.02171** (0.000994)	-0.0000425** (3.93 E-07)	-	-	0.75	8.2
3. 1/f = a + b * <i>TU</i> +c*p+d*p ²	0.0733** (0.0236)	-0.00000385** (4.57 × 10 E-10)	0.0148** (0.00366)	-0.000579** (0.000141)	0.79	6.8
<i>Transplanting to flowering</i>						
1. 1/f = a + b*Tmean	-0.00334ns (0.00359)	+0.000695** (0.00138)	-	-	0.37	12.7
2. 1/f = a + b* <i>TU</i>	0.0302** (0.00117)	-8.64 E-06** (6.44 E-07)	-	-	0.81	7.0
3. 1/f = a + b* <i>TU</i> +c*p+d*p ²	-0.0707* (0.0307)	-8.15 E-06** (8.28 E-07)	+0.0156** (0.00476)	-0.000607** (0.00184)	0.78	6.3

^a*, ** = 0.05 and 0.01 significance levels, respectively, ns = estimated values not significant at the 5% level. 1/f = progress toward flowering, i.e., the reciprocal of the time from seeding to flowering (SF) or transplanting to flowering (TF). p = photoperiod. *TU* = accumulated thermal units. Tmean = mean temperature (°C) from seeding to flowering.

latitude groups. The optimum temperature for maximum development rate in IR36 was 26.8 °C.

A simple model using accumulated thermal units accurately estimated the rate of progress toward flowering (see table). Best fit models included a quadratic photoperiod term (p) that accounted for daylength effects. Models for genotypes maturing earlier (IR9729-67-3 and BG35-2) and later (Taichung Sen Yu 285) than IR36 were very similar in performance.

These data may be useful in developing simulation models of rice growth and development that rely on an accurate prediction of phenological events under a wide range of temperatures and daylengths. □

Grain quality and nutritional value

Optical determination of rice grain chalkiness (Clk)

Jin Qingsheng and Qiu Baiqin, Crop Institute, Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences (ZAAS), Hangzhou, China

We used a digital grain translucency meter (DWY-1A model, manufactured by ZAAS) to measure grain translucency of 17 IR varieties grown in

Grain translucency and Clk rating in milled rice of 17 IR varieties, evaluated by digital translucency meter. Hangzhou, China, 1986.

Variety	Translucency (%)	Clk
IR22	90.7	1.4
IR24	81.0	2.8
IR28	84.0	2.6
IR30	70.0	6.5
IR34	88.0	3.3
IR36	86.3	3.2
IR38	80.7	5.2
IR43	79.7	3.9
IR44	84.3	3.6
IR45	86.7	5.0
IR46	82.3	1.0
IR52	78.7	1.4
IR54	89.0	1.5
IR56	85.0	1.0
IR60	85.7	1.0
IR62	90.7	1.0
IR64	77.3	4.1

early season 1986. Samples of whole milled rice were tested, with three replications.

Mean translucency and corresponding Clk scale are shown in the table. A significant negative correlation was

found between grain translucency and Clk (see figure). For rice breeding work or in grading for market value, this meter can be used instead of visual rating to measure the degree of Clk. Optical determination of Clk is not possible with waxy rice because the opaque endosperm also reduces grain translucency. □

Relationship between Clk scale and translucency measured in milled rice of 17 IR varieties, 1986.